

At the end of inoculation feeding, the seedbox was covered with a 120- × 70- × 35-cm wooden-frame, mylar-film cage with 2-mm-thick, 20-cm-long galvanized-iron wires hanging vertically from the roof of the cage 10 cm apart. The iron tray was filled with water (water level increased at 2 cm/min). As the water level rose, the nymphs gradually moved toward seedling tips and transferred to the overhanging wires. When seedlings were submerged in 5-cm water, the cage was raised and the seedbox gently pulled out. The small cages enclosing the check seedlings were removed.

Another seedbox with fresh seedlings was slid under the cage, water in the iron tray was siphoned out, and the cage was lowered. The cage top was tapped to dislodge the nymphs hanging from the wires and ceiling onto fresh seedlings.

After virus transmission in two batches of seedlings, nymphs were allowed to feed overnight on tungro-infected plants to reacquire the virus.

Seedlings exposed to viruliferous nymphs were compared with control

seedling 3 wk after inoculation and scored on percentage of infected plants.

Two batches of viruliferous nymphs a week can be produced on tungro-infected source plants in an oviposition cage (Fig. 1). The first batch consists of nymphs emerging from eggs laid Mon to Fri; the second, from eggs laid Fri to Mon. Each batch can be used for 2-3 daily inoculations for 5 d. Older nymphs are transferred to TN1 plants in pre-oviposition cages; emerging adults are transferred to oviposition cages to restart the culture.

Using this method, we have screened more than 4,000 germplasm collections and advanced breeding lines. Two accessions of *Oryza latifolia* (IRRI Acc. nos. 105141 and 105142) and one accession of *Oryza officinalis* (IRRI Acc. no. 105220) showed tungro resistance.

To differentiate stunting due to insect feeding from stunting caused by tungro infection, IR29 (vector-resistant but tungro-susceptible) and TN1 (susceptible to both vector and tungro) seedlings were infested for 6 h with 10 or 40

2. Plant height reduction caused by GLH feeding and tungro-infection damage on GLH-resistant IR29 and GLH-susceptible TN1. IRRI, 1990.

viruliferous or nonviruliferous nymphs/seedling. In both cultivars, direct damage by 10 to 40 nymphs/seedling was insignificant. Height reduction due to tungro was significantly higher than that caused by nymphs alone (Fig. 2). ■

Blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) reactions in some wild rices

H. U. Ahmed, N. S. Nahar, A. K. Shahjahan, and S. A. Miah, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRR), Gazipur, Bangladesh; and J. M. Bonman, IRRI

We tested 33 wild rice accessions from IRRI for reactions to leaf BI (*Pyricularia oryzae*) and leaf BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*).

To measure BI reactions, entries were grown in the BI nurseries as the IRBN entries are grown and inoculated at 3- to 4-leaf stage with chopped infected leaf pieces as well as with a spore suspension of *P. oryzae*. Nursery beds were irrigated lightly every afternoon and covered with polyethylene sheets at night to maintain high humidity.

To measure BB reactions, entries were grown in pots following normal cultural practices. They were inoculated at the booting stage with isolate Bxo9 of *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* by the clipping method.

Reactions of some wild rices to leaf BI and BB in Bangladesh.

Name	IRRI acc. no.	BI (% DLA)	BB (% DLA)
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100179	—	—
<i>O. barthii</i>	100117	20.0	—
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	—	—
<i>O. minuta</i>	101089	8.0	—
<i>O. barthii</i>	101380	20.0	12.2
<i>O. nivara</i>	102171	65.0	21.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	102460	65.0	16.2
<i>O. nivara</i>	102463	65.0	15.9
<i>O. nivara</i>	102465	8.0	9.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102467	20.0	9.5
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-2	2.0	25.2
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-3	2.0	35.0
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-5	20.0	22.5
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-6	15.0	28.7
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-7	20.0	26.1
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102468-8	20.0	15.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	102471	20.0	14.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	103406	15.0	6.4
<i>O. nivara</i>	103821	40.0	15.8
<i>O. nivara</i>	103826	—	20.2
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103827-1	35.0	27.6
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103827-2	40.0	33.2
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103828	20.0	21.1
Hybrid Swamp	103829	60.0	33.1
<i>O. nivara</i>	103830	65.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103831	65.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103833	20.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103834	65.0	—
<i>O. nivara</i>	103835	60.0	—
<i>O. nivara</i>	103836	15.0	22.0
<i>O. nivara</i>	103837-1	2.0	25.7
<i>O. nivara</i>	103837-2	2.0	20.6
<i>O. nivara</i>	103840-1	1.0	12.7

Percent diseased leaf area (%DLA) for both B1 and BB was measured three times at 5-d intervals, beginning with initiation of lesions. The table shows final DLA due to B1 and BB. Most entries appear

susceptible to B1 and BB. IRRI Acc. No. 102468-2, 102468-3 (*O. rufipogon/O. nivara*) and 103837-1, 103837-2, and 103840-1 (*O. nivara*) showed resistance to B1; No. 102465 (*O. nivara*) and

102467 and 103406 (*O. rufipogon/O. nivara*) showed resistance to BB.

These wild rices may be used in wide hybridization to transfer resistance genes to cultivated rices. ■

Pest resistance – insects

Evaluation of brown planthopper (BPH)- and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)-resistant hybrid rices for resistance to Angoumois grain moth (AGM)

Wu Jung Tsung, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou, China

AGM *Sitotroga cerealella* Olivier is a major pest of stored rice in China. We evaluated 15 rice hybrids with resistance to BPH or WBPH (Table 1) for their resistance to AGM.

AGM were reared on wheat seeds in the laboratory. Moisture content of rice grain was adjusted to 13%, and 5 g of tested hybrid seed were infested with 100 eggs of AGM. Treatments were in a split-plot design with four replications. After infestation, the samples were stored at 27°C and 75% relative humidity.

Resistance was evaluated on several parameters, including percentage emerging adults, grain weight loss, development period, and susceptibility index (SI). SI was based on the formula

$$SI = \frac{\text{natural log number of emerging adults}}{\text{average development period}} \times 100$$

Susceptibility was determined by this scale:

Damage scale	Emerging adults (%)
Resistant	<10
Moderately resistant	10-20
Susceptible	>20

Table 1. Resistance of hybrids of BPH and WBPH.

Hybrid	CMS/restorer	Reaction ^a	
		BPH	WBPH
Shan You 6	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR24	1	6.3
Shan You 30	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR30	3	7.7
Shan You 54	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR54	1	7
Shan You 56	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR56	2.3	3
Shan You 63	Zhen Shen 97 A/Ming Hui 63	7.7	4.3
Shan You 64	Zhen Shen 97 A/Ce 64 ^b	1.7	2.3
Shan You 177	Zhen Shen 97 A/IR26/Zhai Ye Qing 8	1	1.7
Shan You 6161-8	Zhen Shen 97 A/Gui 8	1.7	3.7
Shan You Zhu Hui Zao	Zhen Shen 97 A/Zhu Hui Zao	1	6.3
Wei You 6	V20 A/IR26	1	3
Wei You 35	V20 A/26 Zhai Zao	1	1.7
Wei You 64	V20A/Ce64 ^c	1	1.7
Wei You 98	V20 A/98	6.3	1.7
Xin You 6	Xin Qing Ai A/IR26	3	4.6
Liu You 30	6064 A/IR30	1.7	9

^aScore 1-9 : 1 = highly resistant, 9 = highly susceptible. ^b IR9761-19-1-64. ^c IR2061/IR661.

Table 2. Resistance of hybrids to AGM.

Hybrid	Emerging adults (%)	Development period (d)	Susceptibility index	Grain weight loss (%)	Damage scale ^a
Shan You 6	18.8	35.2	8.18	3.2	MR
Shan You 30	37.5	27.0	13.45	13.5	S
Shan You 54	23.3	33.3	9.41	8.2	S
Shan You 56	11.0	28.6	8.40	3.4	MR
Shan You 63	25.5	38.4	8.35	9.4	S
Shan You 64	40.5	28.2	13.19	13.6	S
Shan You 177	24.5	33.7	9.48	7.4	S
Shan You 6161-8	25.3	37.9	8.53	9.1	S
Shan You Zhu Hui Zao	42.0	33.1	11.25	11.3	S
Wei You 6	28.0	35.3	9.47	9.3	S
Wei You 35	20.5	34.7	8.68	7.5	S-MR
Wei You 64	34.5	34.3	10.32	12.5	S
Wei You 98	40.5	33.2	10.95	13.3	S
Xin You 6	34.8	26.6	13.30	13.3	S
Liu You 30	39.8	31.7	11.63	13.0	S
Cauvery ^b (resistant check)	4.7	35.6	4.37	0.4	R
Xing Hui Zhan 1 (susceptible check)	43.5	27.4	13.73	8.9	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^b Pureline variety.

No resistant hybrids were found, and only Shan You 6 and Shan You 56 were rated moderately resistant to AGM (Table 2). Shan You 56 was also resistant to both BPH and WBPH, and Shan You 6 exhibited resistance

to BPH. The hybrids were more susceptible to the AGM than were pureline varieties. When 63 pureline varieties were screened for resistance, 36 exhibited resistance and 19 moderate resistance. ■